

Academia of Intellectually Disabled Children in Inclusive and Integrated Schools

Dr. Bhola Vishwakarma

Address- Nariya, Post-B.H.U, Distt-Varanasi,
State-U.P., Pin-221005 (India)
Contact No.– 9307172026
Email Id- bhola.clv@gmail.com

Abstract:

The transition of education paves the way for the children with intellectual disabilities in India. Inclusive Education stands for improvement of schools in all dimensions to deal with the educational needs of all children while Integrated Education way to provide educational opportunities for the moderately intellectual disabled children in the general schooling system and scope of the scheme includes pre-school training, counselling for parents and community involvement. The present study concentrates on the academic performance of children with mild intellectually disabled in inclusive and integrated schools. Though all the school setting is crucial important, yet there will existing substantial difference in their mode of delivering the activity. The purpose of the study is to compare the academic performance of children with mild intellectually disabled in inclusive verses integrated schools. Academic performance for children with mild intellectually disabled assessed through academic area of Functional Assessment Checklist Programme (FACP) tool at primary-I level.

Key words: disability, education, FACP, inclusive, integrated and intellectual

Introduction:

The status of disability in India, particularly in the provision of education and employment for persons with intellectual disabilities, as a matter of need and above all, as a matter of right, has had its recognition only in recent times, almost following the enactment of the Persons with Disabilities Act (PWD), 1995. Educable intellectually disabled children are those who are not able to be adequately educated in the regular classroom. Even so, they can acquire sufficient knowledge and ability in the academic areas that are useful to function effectively in later life. They will be able to acquire basic skills like academic (reading, writing, and arithmetic), social and self-help skill, which supports them to be socially and economically independent. So, the way of an educational programme for the educable group is implementation of children with intellectual disabled in integrated and inclusive education system. Integrated education means children need support in conditions of structural arrangements and teaching methods. Therefore, there is a requirement for special arrangements to assist them in general schools. Integrated education programmes are being implemented in large numbers by both governmental and non-governmental agencies in India. Integrated means the inclusion of children with disabilities in general schools. Modifications are made in the curriculum and the educational and physical environment. Teachers plays an essential role in these modifications like- modifications in environment, teaching approaches, mode instructions, instructional materials, student receptive modes, assessment and evaluation, behavior management approaches and intervention styles. Inclusion means the children with diverse abilities in all aspects of schooling that other children are able to access and enjoy. It involves regular schools and classrooms genuinely adapting and changing to meet the needs of all children, as well as celebrating the valuing variations. This definition does not signify children with diverse abilities will not receive specialized assistance or teaching outside of the classrooms when required, but instead

that this one of many options that are available to, and infect required of all children. Academic performance refers to an acquired high-order ability to perform a task or an activity related to academic. Functional Assessment Checklist Programming (FACP) were used for assessed the academic performance of children with mild intellectually disabled. The area of FACP includes Personal, Social, Academic, Occupational and Recreational. The academic domain of FACP includes number, time, money, reading, writing and functional academic. Students who already achieved 80% of the items in pre-primary checklist are promoted to Primary-I level and the age of the students entering in this class may be seven to ten years approximately.

Review of literature:

Educable mentally retarded (EMR) or Educable Intellectual Disabled children are those who are not able to be adequately educated in the regular classroom. However, they can acquire sufficient knowledge and capability in the academic areas that are useful to function effectively in later life. They will be capable to receive basic academic skills (reading, writing and arithmetic) and self-help skill, which supports them to be socially and economically independent. Therefore the aims of an educational programme for the educable group are, in general, the same as the educational objectives for all children. They must be educated to make the greatest use of their capabilities to fulfill their own needs as well as the demands of the society in which they can be living. Hardiman & et al (2009) made a research to compare the social competence of children with moderate intellectual disability in inclusive versus segregated school settings in the Republic of Ireland. This review shows that children in inclusive schools did not differ significantly from children in segregated schools on the almost all proxy ratings of social competence. On the other hand **Nugent (2007)** compares Inclusive and segregated Settings for children with Dyslexia. This study assessed and compares special educational services for children with dyslexia in three different school types of school. Outcome shows children attending specialist services tended to be more satisfied and more positive about services. Punani (1997) represents a comparative review on effectiveness of various modes of education of visually impaired children. Conclusion of this study uncover that integrated education was the most effective with respect to coverage of special groups such as girls, younger children, congenitally visually impaired children and those coming from traditionally less educated families. However, it was the least effective with regard to the other four parameters. Also Punani (1994) made study in earlier on effectiveness of various modes of education of the person with visually impaired. The research establishes a gradual shift in the preference level from residential to semi-integrated education and from itinerant mode to resource mode of integrated education. **Conrad & Kenneth (1980)** selected fifty primary research studies of special versus regular class placement were selected for use in a meta-analysis. Special classes were found to be significantly inferior to regular class placement for students with below average IQs, and significantly superior to regular classes for behaviorally disordered, emotionally disturbed, and learning-disabled children. All the schools setting are equally important, yet there seems to existing significant difference in their mode of delivering the activity. Since decision makers (Parents, Teachers & Para-professionals) in the education of children with mild mental retardation face contradictory opinions, the study of educational models is imperative and felt as the need of the hour.

Objectives of the study:

- To study the academic performance of children with mild intellectually disabled in integrated education system.
- To study the academic performance of children with mild intellectually disabled in inclusive education system.

- To compare the academic performance of children with mild intellectually disabled in integrated and inclusive education system.

Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference in the academic performance of children with mild intellectually disabled in integrated and inclusive schools.

Methodology:

The present study focused at comparing academic performance of children with mild intellectually disabled in inclusive verses integrated schools. Academic performance for children with mild intellectual disabled assessed through academic skill areas of Functional Assessment Checklist Programme (FACP), a standard tool developed by National Institute for Mentally Handicapped (renamed National Institute for the Empowerment of Person with Intellectual Disabilities, Secunderabad). The researcher selected only 40 items from academic skills areas of FACP checklist to assess the academic performance of the sample. These items were chosen from the standardized FACP tool at primary-I level of academic domain. To examine the items of the tools, the investigator well prepared and also collected appropriate materials to check the performance of the sample.

The samples of the present study were mild intellectually disabled children studied in two different types of school setting one integrated and another was inclusive school. The group of this study was 10 students in each group and age from 7 to 10 years for each type of schools. So, the sample from integrated school is $N_1=10$ and from inclusive school is $N_2=10$, there was total sample size $N=20$. For the study the researcher were selected two integrated school and four inclusive schools from Coimbatore district of Tamil Nadu state of India. Hence the investigator selected purposive sampling technique.

With prior authorization of Head of the school, the investigator acquired a face to face contact with the sample. After establishing sufficient rapport with the sample, the investigator requested to the subjects to perform the activities as per tool one by one with the help of earlier prepared teaching learning materials. Through keen observation of the performance of the sample, the investigator made an assessment with the tool. The present study focuses on the comparison of academic performance of children with mild intellectually disabled. Hence the investigator selected ex-post facto research design for the study.

The collected data was tabulated and consolidated for further statistical treatment. The two group data was then subjected to quantitative analysis, using t-test with two-tail and find whether there is no significant difference in the academic performance of children with mild intellectual disabled in integrated and inclusive schools.

T-test, Academic performance comparison between groups

Skills	Group	N	Mean	S.D	't'
Academic Performance	Inclusive School	10	27.5000	7.1375	1.684
	Integrated School	10	32.0000	4.5216	

The result of the table reveals that the mean score of academic performance of children studied in inclusive schools is 27.50 and integrated schools is 32.00 with t-value 1.684. The calculated t-value is $t(18) = 1.684$ ($P < 0.05$). The result shows that there is no significant difference in academic performance of children with mild intellectually disabled in inclusive and integrated schools.

Result and Discussion:

The calculated t-test value is 1.684 which is less than the table value of 2.101 at 5% level of significance. Since the calculated value is less than the table value it is inferred that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of children with mild intellectually disabled in inclusive and integrated schools. Hence the hypothesis is retained. Also, some studies have been done with relevant to this study which supports. Hardiman & et al. (2009) suggest that children with moderate mental retardation in inclusive schools did not differ significantly from children in segregated schools on ratings of social competence. There is no significant difference between integrated and inclusive schools with the reference to academic competency of children with mild mental retardation. But the mean value of children of integrated school ($m_1=32.00$) is much better than inclusive schools ($m_2=27.50$). Therefore an integrated school is better in comparison to inclusive school in the form of academic competencies of children with mild intellectually disabled.

Recommendations:

- Teacher should improve their teaching strategies to serve better education to children with intellectually disabled in inclusive as well as integrated school.
- Professional working in the field of special education can understand that inclusive education is not only universal learning system also in some cases integrated education is more beneficial.
- Parent of intellectually disabled children should be observed time to time for progress of their child.
- Futuristic researcher can be study on large sample size and analysis could be done on more number of variables likes gender, socio-economic status, age, etc.

Conclusion:

It is evident from the above research studies that, there is no much difference in academic performance for children with mild intellectually disabled. Our research also shows that integrated school is providing better educational in some situation. Due to lack of time and manpower study were conducted only with a small sample size of few schools of Coimbatore district also various extraneous and intervening variables affecting the children at the time of assessment was not fully controlled. This is the era of inclusion, but result shows that now we are far from concept of inclusion cause mentioned earlier. Inclusive education will become best educational model after modifying and adapting necessary programme in the schools.

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